

D8.3 Project Dissemination material

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List of abbreviations

<Abbreviation>	<Explanation>
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FP7	Seventh Framework Programme
GESIS	GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
Gov2u	Government To You
HS	Hansard Society
ITI	University of Southampton IT Innovation
KMI	Open University, Knowledge Media Institute
UKOM	University Koblenz – Landau
SU	Stockholm University
M1	Month 1, M3=Month 3 etc.
LOD	Linked Open Data
Y1	Year 1
Y2	Year 2
Y3	Year 3

Executive summary

SENSE4US was launched in October 2013, with the aim to research ways in order to make policy-making more effective with the use of cutting edge research and technologies. The online tool that was developed by the project partners gathers and summarizes information from multiple sources (i.e. open data, citizen generated data, forums etc.), thus helping policy makers find and use effectively the most relevant and updated information when forming policies; also it enables policy-makers to simulate the impacts and consequences of different policy options as if they were enacted.

D8.3 “Project Dissemination materials” is a deliverable of WP8 Communication and Exploitation to be delivered in M39. It presents the updated version of the promotional materials as well as new materials that were created for the third year of project’s implementation.

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the updated version of the dissemination materials that were created and subsequently uploaded on the project website. A short description about each of these materials and their screen shots are included in the deliverable and its Appendices. The promotional materials are part of the project’s external communication and as such they will be updated regularly as the project progresses, highlighting its developments.

Section 1 includes the full list of the dissemination materials that were produced for the internal and external promotion and marketing of the project. Therefore, the press release, the newsletter, the brochure, poster and flyer are briefly discussed. Furthermore, a number of figures are included in this chapter and in the Appendices, offering a visual presentation of the materials to the reader.

Section 2 presents briefly the project website (www.sense4us.eu), which is designed, developed and operated by Gov2u. It is the major dissemination and information channel of the project; it includes all relevant information to the project and the dissemination materials as well. A reference is also made in this chapter to the Social Media profiles that were created for the project (Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn).

Section 3 is dedicated to the conclusions highlighting the important role of the dissemination materials for the promotion of the project throughout its duration.

1 Dissemination materials

The updated versions of the dissemination materials were created by WP8 in order to be used by the project partners in their dissemination activities and thus maximize their impact and help raise awareness of the project.

Moreover project partners have created promotional materials for the Final Brussels Conference and London event in order to raise the visibility of SENSE4US, attract more stakeholders and engage them.

The materials that were created by the SENSE4US consortium during the reporting period are the following:

- [Updated project brochure](#)
- [Flyer](#)
- [Brussels conference invitation](#)
- [Conference poster](#)
- [Case study video](#) (Brussels conference)
- Flyer (London event)
- Presentation of a case study (London event)
- Agenda (Brussels conference),
- Speaker bios (Brussels conference),
- Sense4us information pack (Brussels conference),
- EU conference poster - Copyrights (Brussels conference),
- EU conference poster - Policy modelling (Brussels conference),
- EU conference poster - Senti circles (Brussels conference),
- EU conference poster - Text index analysis (Brussels conference),
- EU conference poster - LOD (Brussels conference)

More detailed the materials are being presents in this chapter of the deliverable

1.1 Project Brochure

A single sheet, letter size, three-fold brochure in English, with a clean, modern and attractive design was created for dissemination purposes. The external side of the brochure presents the project logo & name and contains various project information (website, consortium members, the programme under which it has been funded and the logo of the European Commission). The front page presents the four modules the project is developing. The fourth module is being presented on the external side of the brochure. The external side is being presented in figure 1 below.

D8.3 Project Dissemination materials

POLICY IMPACT ANALYSIS

This module will assist policy makers in evaluating policy options. Simulation techniques support the policy development process by analysing the potentially unseen impacts of a proposed policy and allowing different scenarios to be tested and their consequences assessed. The insights obtained from the simulations can inform a comprehensive policy impact assessment.

PROJECT CONSORTIUM PARTNERS:

- UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON
IT INNOVATION CENTRE
www.it-innovation.soton.ac.uk
- THE OPEN UNIVERSITY, KMI
www.kmi.open.ac.uk
- UNIVERSITY KOBLENZ-LANDAU
www.west.uni-koblenz.de
- GOVERNMENT TO YOU
www.gov2u.org
- GESIS - LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE FOR THE SOCIAL SCIENCES
www.gesis.org/en/institute
- HANSARD SOCIETY
www.hansardsociety.org.uk
- STOCKHOLM UNIVERSITY
www.dsv.su.se/en

QUESTIONS?
Contact us: info@sense4us.eu

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SENSE4US PROJECT

SENSE4US

DATA INSIGHTS FOR
POLICY MAKERS & CITIZENS

THEME ANALYSIS
Providing automatic summaries of policy documents

SENTIMENT ANALYSIS
Summarising opinions and sentiment from social media

LINKED OPEN DATA SEARCH
Discovering, interlinking and recommending the most relevant data sources

POLICY IMPACT ANALYSIS
Simulating the impact of proposed policy options on citizens and society

QR CODE
WWW.SENSE4US.EU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme

Figure 1 : Project Brochure (external side)

THE SENSE4US TOOLBOX

The project assists policy makers by providing novel tools and techniques that are intended to make sense of the overwhelming quantity of information that may be relevant to a policy, and by helping to examine the impact of a proposed policy on society. Sense4us has developed an integrated toolkit to help policy makers access and summarise a wide array of relevant data, take into account the views of citizens on policy issues and better understand the implications of proposed policies.

THEME ANALYSIS

This module analyses and identifies topics from any document using text analysis and machine learning. The topics extracted provide the user with a quick summary of the document or group of documents, so the user can make a quick judgement about which ones are more relevant or useful, without having to read them all.

An additional benefit of the thematic analysis is that the keywords extracted from the documents may be used for further, more detailed, searches in open data repositories or on social media platforms.

SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

The emergence of social media has given citizens a space to share their thoughts and opinions on all kinds of topics and events. Sense4us will provide tools that summarise social media discussions and extract the key sentiments and opinions of citizens towards a policy or related political issue. These tools will therefore allow policy makers to tune into a wide variety of citizens' reactions to policies and political issues, all of which will contribute to more informed policy decisions.

LINKED OPEN DATA SEARCH

This module will recommend the most relevant data sources based on the analysis of a document or search terms entered by the policy maker, and will execute distributed searches across multiple data repositories. Links between the data sources will be indicated, so the user can explore themes and datasets related to the policy, potentially discovering new information on previously unexplored topics.

Figure 2 : Project Brochure (internal side)

In the internal part of the brochure the remaining three of the four modules are being presented in an easy to understand language, even by non-technical audiences. (See figure 2 below).

The brochure is developed in order to be distributed for communication/dissemination and awareness raising purposes to stakeholders with an interest in Sense4us during local events, conferences, workshops or road shows. The brochure is available on the public website, under the “Promotional Material” section of the Work Packages tab, as well as in the project News. A printable version of the brochure has also been distributed to the partners via the sharing tool the consortium is using.

1.2 Project Flyer

A single sheet in A5 size, which in its front page displays the logo and QR code of the project, EC logo. The back page presents the final version of the Toolbox and the social media of SENSE4US.

The flyer is developed in order to be distributed for communication/ dissemination and inform the stakeholders about the final version of the Toolbox.

Figure 3 : Project Flyer (Front side)

Sense4us Information Discovery Toolbox

POLICY MODELLING & SIMULATION

This tool helps users structure a public policy decision, assess the potential impact of it, and evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness of policy options.

Users can create a policy simulation model using a check-list (information tree) editor, and the labeled causal map graphing canvas to plot actors, variables, control flows and causal dependencies.

The project assists policy makers by providing novel tools and techniques that are intended to make sense of the overwhelming quantity of information that may be relevant to a policy, and by helping to examine the impact of a proposed policy on society. Sense4us has developed an integrated toolkit to help policy makers access and summarise a wide array of relevant data, take into account the views of citizens on policy issues and better understand the implications of proposed policies.

THEME ANALYSIS
Providing automatic summaries of policy documents

SENTIMENT ANALYSIS
Summarising opinions and sentiment from social media

LINKED OPEN DATA SEARCH
Discovering, interlinking and recommending the most relevant data sources

POLICY IMPACT ANALYSIS
Simulating the impact of proposed policy options on citizens and society

f
SENSE4US-PROJECT

t
@SENSE4USPROJECT

in
SENSE4US PROJECT

Figure 4 : Project Flyer (Back side)

1.3 Brussels Conference Invitation

The invitation was created and distributed to stakeholders in order to inform the general audience about the final conference of SENSE4US project and raise its visibility. The invitation includes the logo of the project, EC logo, partners' logos and a short description about the topics that will be discussed as well as the date, time and venue.

The Sense4us project would like to cordially invite you to its upcoming conference themed:

**Policy making in a complex world:
Can technology restore trust in European decision-making?**

Join parliamentarians, policy makers and academics as they take a look at how new technologies can help to better support our democracy.

The one day event will take place on

**Thursday 8th December, 2016
09:00-17:00 CET**

@Hotel Sofitel Brussels Europe, 1 Place Jourdan, Brussels, BE

Find the complete agenda and see the list of our speakers [here!](#)

Register Now!

Free Event

Figure 5 : Brussels Conference Invitation

1.4 Brussels Conference Poster

The poster was created in order to raise the visibility of the conference and inform the general audience. The poster includes the logo of the project, EC logo, partners' logos and a short description about the topics that will be discussed as well as the date, time and venue.

SENSE4US

POLICY MAKING IN A COMPLEX WORLD:
Can technology restore trust in European decision-making?

JOIN THE DISCUSSION!
Parliamentarians, policy makers and academics look at how new technologies can best enable the support of our democracy

REGISTER NOW!
Free Event

THURSDAY 8TH DECEMBER, 2016
09:00-17:00 CET

@HOTEL SOFITEL BRUSSELS EUROPE,
1 PLACE JOURDAN, BRUSSELS, BE

Can technology can lead to new era of "anticipatory governance"?

Co-creation & participatory design - the key to trust & transparency for policy making?

What are the big, open & linked data challenges in policy making?

Explore the Sense4us information discovery toolbox!

SENSE4US, European Commission, Southampton University, KIM, egovlab, GESIS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no. 611242

Figure 6 : Brussels Conference Poster

1.5 Case Study video

ITI has created a case study video for presenting it to the Final Brussels Conference. The video can be viewed by clicking on the following link:

https://www.amazon.co.uk/cloudrive/share/BXcmGqwNkQLrYFCKI27BxZnCbGO7SnfebJMpb7RcWOr?encoding=UTF8&mgh=1&ref=cd_ph_share_link_copy&v=grid

Figure 7 : Case study video

1.6 Flyer for London event

Figure 8 : Flyer for London Event (external side)

The internal side of the flyer features the SENSE4US logo and three main sections:

- Information discovery toolbox**: Start with a policy subject and discover:
 - What themes are buried inside documents
 - What themes are important to people
 - What their opinions are
 - Which influential people to consult
 - Information related to the policy subject
 - Impact of policy
- Document summarization**: Discover themes and their importance. This section shows two screenshots of a web interface. The first screenshot shows a table of key words and their occurrences. The second screenshot shows a list of clusters with 'Policy and Security' selected.
- Sentiment analysis**: Discover popular sentiment on each topic. This section shows a grid of sentiment analysis charts for various dates from Oct 25 to Nov 3. A red callout box points to a chart on Oct 28-29, stating 'Event causing change in sentiment'.
- Policy modelling**: Explore potential impact of policy. This section shows a complex network diagram with nodes and connecting lines, representing relationships between different entities or topics.

Figure 9 : Flyer for London Event (internal side)

1.7 Case study presentation (London event)

>> SENSE4US www.sense4us.eu
 Finding themes in Evidence
 Case Study: Investigatory Powers Bill Evidence

Project co-funded by the European Union under the Seventh Framework Programme
 © Copyright by the SENSE4US Consortium

>> Summarising Evidence

- A researcher is tasked with summarising a large amount of information
 - E.g. 1500 page evidence document
 - Often in very short time
 - And over the holiday period ...
- Using traditional approach:
 - Work through document with highlight pen
 - Pull out what looks like important issues & themes
- Disadvantage:
 - Massively time-consuming
 - Intensive on human resources
 - Error prone
 - Demoralising !

>> Sense4us Helps the Researcher

- Helps the researcher identify themes in the document
 - Ready for human interpretation and reporting
 - Includes supporting evidence from the document
 - Distributions of sentiment on document themes
- Saves time
 - Parsing and indexing process took about 6 minutes for a 1,532 page document (IPB written evidence) on a laptop

Figure 10 : Case study presentation (London event)

1.8 Agenda & Speaker bios (Brussels conference)

Policy-making in a Complex World: Can Technology Restore Trust in European Decision-making?

Agenda

09:00 – 09:30	Registration and coffee
09:30 – 09:40	Welcome / opening remarks <ul style="list-style-type: none">Paul Walland, IT Innovation, Southampton University & Project Co-ordinator, Sense4us
09:40 – 11:00	What matters? Building trust in the policy making process <u>Moderator:</u> Vasilis Koulolias, Executive Director, eGovlab, Stockholm University <u>Speakers:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none">Professor Maria Wimmer, Institute for Information Systems Research, University of KoblenzDr Ruth Fox, Director, Hansard SocietyAndrea Halmos, Policy Officer, European Commission, DG CONNECT, eGovernment and TrustMichael Psallidas, Managing Director, Crowdpolicy
11:00 – 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 – 12:50	BOLD decision-making: the marriage of governance and data <u>Moderator:</u> Frank Leyman, Manager of International Relations, FEDICT

Figure 11 : Brussels conference agenda page 1

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	<p><u>Speakers:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stefan Klauser, Project Leader, "Digital Society", Computational Social Science COSS • Dr Aron Larsson, Researcher, eGovlab, Stockholm University • Paul Walland, IT Innovation, Southampton University / Project Co-ordinator, Sense4us
12:50 – 14:00	Lunch
14:00 – 15:00	<p>Making sense of the noise: understanding the 'chaotic pluralism' of online political discussion</p> <p><u>Moderator:</u> Paul Walland, IT Innovation, Southampton University / Project Co-ordinator, Sense4us</p> <p><u>Speakers:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Miriam Fernandez, Research Fellow, Knowledge Media Institute, Open University • Steven Ginnis, Head of Digital Research at the Social Research Institute, Ipsos Mori • Oktavia Jonsdottir, Deputy MP, Icelandic Pirate Party
15:00 – 15:15	Coffee break
15:15 – 16:15	<p>Co-creation and innovation: building trust through participatory design</p> <p><u>Moderator:</u> Francisco García Morán, Chief IT Advisor, European Commission</p> <p><u>Speakers:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cat Drew, Uscreates and former Senior Policy Advisor, Policy Lab UK, Cabinet Office • Vasilis Koulolias, Executive Director, eGovlab, Stockholm University • Paul Walland, IT Innovation, Southampton University /

Figure 12 : Brussels conference agenda page 2

	Project Co-ordinator, Sense4us
16:15 – 16:20	<p>Closing remarks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paul Walland, IT Innovation, Southampton University / Project Co-ordinator, Sense4us

Figure 13 : Brussels conference agenda page 3

Speakers

Cat Drew

Cat is Projects Director at Uscreates which provides user-centred design and communication services to health and wellbeing organisations. Before joining Uscreates, Cat worked as a Senior Policy Advisor in the UK Cabinet Office's Policy Lab, working with Government departments to promote design-based techniques in policymaking, including data science and visualisation, behavioural insights and prototyping. She also worked at the Home Office as Head of Police IT and Digitisation Policy.

Miriam Fernandez

Research Fellow at the Knowledge Media Institute at the Open University, a Sense4us project partner, Miriam's research focuses on the analysis of online communities within the social web, including user needs and behaviour, and the development of prediction models to evaluate the opportunities and risks surrounding these communities. Prior to joining the Open University, Miriam worked at Google and as a Research Associate at the Universidad Autonoma de Madrid.

Ruth Fox

Ruth is the Director of the Hansard Society, a Sense4us project partner and political research and education charity, working to strengthen parliamentary democracy in the UK and around the world. She is the co-author of the Audit of Political Engagement, the only annual health check on the state of British democracy. Her other research interests focus on constitutional reform, the role and function of Members of Parliament, and the parliamentary legislative and scrutiny process. Prior to joining the Society Ruth worked as a political adviser to an MP and UK government minister.

Figure 14 : Brussels conference speakers' bios page 1

Steven Ginnis

Steven is an Associate Director and Head of Innovation at Ipsos MORI, where he is responsible for pioneering the use of new and emerging technologies in public sector research, including mobile, neuroscience, and social media. He directed the Wisdom of the Crowd project, working with the Centre for Analysis of Social Media at Demos and the University of Sussex, to help embed rigour and ethics into social media research. More recently, Steven led the Dialogue on Data Science Ethics commissioned by the Government Data Science Partnership, which explored public attitudes towards the use of data science by governments.

Andrea Halmos

Policy Officer at the European Commission Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content & Technology (DG CONNECT), Andrea's work explores the future of public services through open government, the Commission's eGovernment Action Plan and the Digital Single Market. Before joining DG CONNECT, Andrea supported the deployment of trans-European digital services in government, education, health and business for the Commission's eTEN programme, and worked as case handler at the Directorate General for Competition. Prior to joining the European Commission, she worked for an internet start-up as a sourcing consultant.

Oktavía Jónsdóttir

Elected Deputy MP for the Icelandic Pirate Party in October's general election, Oktavía supported the crowdfunded campaign that increased the party's representation in the Althing from three to 10 seats – enough to initiate coalition negotiations. Oktavía's background is in media, conflict and ICT, and she has extensive experience in digital security and safety as an independent advisor and member of the team that created the secure hosting platform VirtualRoad, a service that mitigates DDoS attacks on online news outlets and Human Rights organizations.

Figure 15 : Brussels conference speakers' bios page 2

Stefan Klauser

Lead Strategist for 'Digital Society' at the Department for Computational Social Science, ETH Zurich, Stefan has led projects in areas such as FinTech and participatory networks, and oversees the programme's strategy, community engagement and outreach. A political scientist, he is also Co-founder and Development Manager of the Blockchain & Internet of Things Summer School, which promotes the education and advancement of these emerging technologies. Before joining ETH Zurich, Stefan worked for the Swiss Department of Foreign Affairs and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation, where he served as Project Leader for Innovation Initiatives and Swiss Representative to the OECD Global Science Forum.

Vasilis Koulolias

Vasilis is the Director and Founder of eGovLab, a laboratory researching eGovernment and citizen service delivery at Stockholm University's Department of Computer Science and a Sense4us project partner. Until recently, he was also Executive Director of Gov2u, which advises governments on how to modernize their policy development processes, and now serves as their Chairman of the Board. Vasilis is a member of the International Council for Information Technology in Government Administration (ICA), and prior to Gov2u served as Executive Director of access2democracy, an NGO promoting participatory e-democracy. In 1987 he established Pythia Corp, a legislative information systems service.

Aron Larsson

Researcher at the eGovLab, a Sense4us project partner, and Associate Professor of Systems Analysis and Security at the University of Stockholm, Aron's research examines the development of computational methods for interactive risk and decision analysis in areas such as public policy, investment and environmental management. Aron has published widely on topics ranging from policy modelling to the management of complex flood-risk management decisions.

Figure 16 : Brussels conference speakers' bios page 3

Frank Leyman

Frank is Manager International Relations for FEDICT, the Belgian Federal Public Service for Information and Communication Technology. In this capacity he represents Belgium at the European Commission, co-ordinates policy issues with EU member states, is a member of the OECD's e-Leaders group and a member of the EU's eGovernment Action Plan Steering Group. He is also chairman of the IDM Expert Group at the World Bank and a former chairman of the ICA. Prior to joining FEDICT he worked for STMicroelectronics, Belgacom, and IBM.

Francisco Garcia Moran

Chief IT Adviser at the European Commission, Francisco provides strategic advice on a range of major IT issues, particularly focusing on implementation of eGovernance within the Commission. He previously served as Director General of IT at the Commission focusing on making effective and efficient use of information and communication technologies in order to achieve the Commission's organisational and political objectives. He has had responsibility for defining the IT strategy of the Commission, and implementing IT infrastructure solutions and e-services.

Michael Psalidas

Michael is Co-founder and Managing Director of Crowdpolicy, a crowdsourcing organisation that develops platforms and applications to encourage collaboration in decision-making processes in the public and private sectors. He is also the Co-founder and Managing Director of SocialBank, which specialises in financial technology for social and development banking. Michael previously served as Senior Consultant in Public Information Systems to the Vice President of the Greek Government and is a member of the Harvard Business Review Advisory Council.

Paul Walland

Sense4us project lead and Innovation Director at the IT Innovation Centre, University of Southampton, Paul oversees applied research projects, leading future thinking on the direction of technology development and extracting impact from project outcomes. With over 25 years'

Figure 17 : Brussels conference speakers' bios page 4

D8.3 Project Dissemination materials

experience developing and running applied research projects in industry and academia, Paul's research interests include media and social networks, their evolution and the impact of technology on social evolution and communication. Before joining IT Innovation Paul was Research Manager at Snell & Wilcox, a UK media company, and GEC Marconi, working on the introduction of digital television.

Maria Wimmer

Professor for eGovernment at the at University of Koblenz-Landau, Maria's research examines open- and e-government, e-democracy and systems analysis and design, including security modelling and knowledge management for e-government, public sector IT and the semantic web. Maria also chairs the eGovernment Research Group at Koblenz's Institute for Information Systems, and before gaining academic tenure was part of the cabinet-level ICT Operative Unit within the Federal Chancellery of Austria, where her work included education concept designs for e-government.

The Sense4us project is funded by the European Commission under the Seventh Framework Programme (grant 611242).

Figure 18 : Brussels conference speakers' bios page 5

Sense4us consortium partners

Figure 19 : Brussels conference agenda last page

1.9 Sense4us information pack (Brussels conference)

An Information Discovery Support Toolkit

This project is funded by the European Commission under the Seventh Framework Programme (grant 611242).

Figure 20 : Brussels conference info pack

1.10 EU conference poster - Copyrights (Brussels conference)

Figure 21 : Brussels conference – Copyrights page 1

Figure 22 : Brussels conference – Copyrights page 2

EU COPYRIGHT REFORM ANALYSIS

STAGE FIVE

U	show	50	50
<input type="checkbox"/>	exception	47	50
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	research	41	47
<input type="checkbox"/>	copyright	35	41
<input type="checkbox"/>	content	33	38

Text in Cluster

Show: 10 entries Search:

Doc Name	Num	Sentence
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TEXT AND DATA MINING CONSULTATION ANSWERS only.docx	41	Although text and data mining is concerned with the extraction of facts and data, the results of text and data mining research are currently being suppressed because of a lack of legal clarity.
<input type="checkbox"/> TEXT AND DATA MINING CONSULTATION	77	While this is an important EU concern, the research community should be offered more flexibility in particular when deciding at what stage anonymisation is required.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Copyright	4
<input type="checkbox"/>	Require	4
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other Topics	4
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Concern	3

Surrounding Text

Show: 10 entries Search:

Num	Sentence
39	Because it prevents the copying of large portions of databases, the Database Directive is also a legal barrier to text and data mining.
40	Technical protection measures (also protected under law), preventing the downloading of large amounts of content, are also preventing the application of text and data mining techniques.
41	Although text and data mining is concerned with the extraction of facts and data, the results of text and data mining research are currently being suppressed because of a lack of legal clarity.

Text index analysis of consultation results for text and data mining

Further evidence of lack of legal clarity

CONCLUSIONS

- The manual analysis concluded that there are two key obstacles to text and data mining: legal **uncertainty** on whether and how copyright might apply; and problems with existing, inadequate, **licensing mechanisms**.*
- The Sense4us text index analysis identifies these exact same points. With Sense4us, the work was less labour intensive than the manual analysis: it took just 7 minutes to create the index for 2,500 pages of text.

* Source: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52016SC0301&qid=1474725118228>

This project has received funding from the EU's Seventh Framework Programme (grant 611242).

Figure 23 : Brussels conference – Copyrights page 3

1.11 EU conference poster - Policy modelling (Brussels conference)

POLICY MODELLING AND SIMULATION

INTRODUCTION

- This tool helps users structure a public policy decision, assess the potential impact of it, and evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness of policy options.
- Users can create a policy simulation model using a check-list (information tree) editor, and the labelled causal map graphing canvas to plot actors, variables, control flows and causal dependencies.

APPROACH

Systems analysis for policy that involves:

- Conceptual analysis: using a policy-oriented problem structuring method, labelled causal mapping.
- Empirical analysis: simulation-based impact assessment (simulation of scenarios of change).
- Operational analysis: ex ante evaluation of policy options based on the simulation results and using a common policy appraisal format.

Users can construct and validate sub-models to build a complex model. Time step and number of iterations are defined for scenario simulation.

POLICY MODELLING AND SIMULATION PLATFORM

Policy problem: Finland's Immigration Crisis

- Sub problems**
 - Asylum applications – processing – decisions
 - Resettlement and settlement of refugees
 - Ensuring safety and security
 - Integration of immigrants
- Official actors**
 - Ministry of the Interior
 - Finnish Immigration Service
 - The Police and Border Guard
 - The Ministry for Employment and the Economy
 - The Ministry of Social Affairs and Health
 - The Ministry of Education and Culture
- Policy Instruments**
 - Economic**
 - Financial: Expenditure on social benefits
 - Financial: Subsidies for non-profitable reception centers & services
 - Financial: Funding language training programs
 - Financial: Participation in EU border control operations PROKTES
 - Human: Private funding for housing and employment programs
 - Regulatory**
 - Signaling of immigration policies & timely realization
 - Effective status of returned applications and removal of serious offenders
 - Informational**
 - Knowledge about the asylum policies and processes
 - Capacity building**
 - Recruiting new employees (Police and Immigration service)
 - Enhancing the accuracy of asylum applications
 - Data integration from different authorities
 - Cooperation**
 - Reconciliation & involvement of refugees from other EU countries
 - External factors and constraints**
 - Refugee camps in Turkey
 - Migration flows to EU
- Policy Impacts**
 - Financial**
 - Costs on gov. authorities
 - Infrastructure-related**
 - Reception services
 - Municipal services for immigrants
 - Social**
 - Number of asylum applications
 - Processing time of applications
 - Accepted refugees
 - Illegal immigrants
 - Immigration returns
 - Integration to society
 - Work and well-being of immigrants
 - Criminal cases
 - Discrimination cases
 - Economic**
 - Unemployment rate / Laborer availability / Low salary labor
 - Domestic demand
 - Tax income

DEMO

- This example is a prescriptive policy analysis for Finland's immigration crisis, modelling and simulating the Finnish government's actions in response to the increasing number of asylum seekers.
- It is a systems model showing the policy instrument variables, policy impact variables, and causal links (direction, sign, change transfer co-efficients and time lags).
- The model shows a scenario of change and the simulation results in terms of percentage changes relative to a baseline.

This project has received funding from the EU's Seventh Framework Programme (grant 611242).

Figure 24 : Brussels conference – Policy Modelling

1.12 EU conference poster - Senti circles (Brussels conference)

SENTI CIRCLES SENSE4US

INTRODUCTION

- Sentiment analysis, particularly over social streams, offers users a fast and effective way to monitor the public's feelings towards policies.
- The Senti Circles platform captures feedback from text based sources – e.g. consultation documents or social media conversations – applying contextual and conceptual sentiment analysis to identify the sentiment expressed in them.
- It provides a novel sentiment navigation design where contextual sentiment is captured and presented at term/entity levels, enabling a better alignment of positive and negative sentiment to the nature of the public debate.

APPROACH TO SENTIMENT

'Renewable energy' is a term found in a tweet collection that we want to examine for sentiment. The terms that co-occur with this term in the tweet collection are 'charging', 'subsidies', 'advances', 'clean' etc.

'Renewable Energy' as the key term is positioned at the centre of the SentiCircle. The terms that co-occur with 'Renewable Energy' in the tweet collection (context) will be positioned in the SentiCircle considering:

- The number of times they co-occur together in the tweet collection
- The polarity of the terms (extracted from a sentiment lexicon)

SENTIMENT ANALYSIS PLATFORM

Keywords:

Name	# Tweets	Correlation of Sentiment	# Related Terms
law	6548	0.576	4472
movement	6248	-0.508	4412
is	4854	-0.456	4120
uk	3001	0.395	1480
single	2323	-0.401	1948
market	2108	0.470	1802
body	1828	0.555	1058
deal	1818	-0.306	214
brexit	1478	-0.404	758
@DavidMil291143	1180	-0.406	80
voted	967	-0.401	241
move	881	-0.400	708
law	860	0.708	289
joined	847	0.581	42
word	827	-0.507	347

Sentiment Distribution for Tweets Containing law

Related Items for Selected Keyword: law

Name	Correlation
(NOT) supremacy	0.478
(NOT) met	0.431
(NOT) Reg	0.433
(NOT) money	0.433
(NOT) end	0.382
interests	0.345
question	0.321

DEMO

- 9643 tweets from the hashtag Europe Free Movement. This took 18.15 minutes to run.
- Visualisation shows the sentiment is neutral to negative.
- In the considered context "law" is one of the terms receiving more negative sentiment. It co-occurs with 289 related terms. The term "(NOT) supremacy" is one of the highest correlated terms.
- Beneath the tables, the individual tweets are highlighted with user and location information in addition to the sentiment of the entire tweet.
- Further developments are planned to integrate user role categorisation (e.g. political, media, civil society, business).

This project has received funding from the EU's Seventh Framework Programme (grant 611242).

Figure 25 : Brussels conference – Senti circles

1.13 EU conference poster - Text index analysis (Brussels conference)

TEXT INDEX ANALYSIS

INTRODUCTION

- Researchers often have to analyse significant volumes of text based information within tight time constraints.
- At present they are largely reliant on manual analysis to determine the key themes and sub-themes within documents. This is labour intensive and prone to error and potential bias.
- Text Index Analysis enables users to quickly discover and classify entities in documents thereby enhancing understanding of the key themes and saving valuable staff resources.

APPROACH TO TEXT ANALYSIS

- Having uploaded a text based document for analysis, the tool constructs an index of key words highlighting both the number of sentences in which the word appears, and the number of occurrences in the document overall.
- Clusters for selected keywords then provide more detailed analysis of the thematic content.
- Users can quickly access all the occurrences of those keywords/clusters in the document, and view them in the surrounding context.

TEXT ANALYSIS PLATFORM

DEMO

- The written evidence submitted to the Joint Committee on the Investigatory Powers Bill at Westminster ran to 1,632 pages.
- The tool took just 29 seconds to create an index of keywords and related word clusters.
- Manual analysis of the documentation by committee staff took days by comparison.
- Once stop-words had been removed the most commonly occurring keyword was 'Data' – there were 30 cluster words associated with it.
- Of these, 'Data Retention' was the second most commonly occurring word cluster, appearing 11 times in the document.
- Within minutes the key themes of the document can be identified, enabling users to drill down to the discussion about these themes.

This project has received funding from the EU's Seventh Framework Programme (grant 611242).

Figure 26 : Brussels conference – Text index analysis

1.14 EU conference poster - LOD Search (Brussels conference)

LINKED OPEN DATA SEARCH

INTRODUCTION

- Linked Open Data provides users with an overview of related information in different datasets.
- Connecting related information from different sources the LOD platform visualises the connections, their weighting, and the types of links that are captured.
- It provides new opportunities for enhanced stakeholder analysis by getting beyond the 'usual suspects'.

APPROACH TO LOD

- The LOD search captures connections between selected resources via Unified Resource Identifiers (URI's) in datasets.
- It then weights the connections depending on the relationship between the selected terms.
- It visualises the weighted relationships, displaying information about the ranking of paths.

LOD PLATFORM

DEMO

- Like the other Sense4us tools, the LOD search is designed to use a range of languages. The example above shows links to the term "wind energy" in German.
- The English language example shows links from the "UK" to "David Cameron" in DBpedia. This illustrates the potential to find new links between terms in the LOD cloud - this could be particularly useful when decision makers want to reach beyond the "usual suspects", for example to supply evidence about policy issues.

This project has received funding from the EU's Seventh Framework Programme (grant 611242).

Figure 27 : Brussels conference – LOD Search

1.15 Project Newsletter

The Sense4us newsletter was designed in the beginning of the project. During the reporting period (October 2015 – December 2016) three issues have been circulated (February 2016, May 2016 and December 2016). Its main section is devoted on the project news, while there are also sections for other interesting news on policy-making and a dedicated section about upcoming events and interesting publications. All newsletter issues were targeted and delivered to key stakeholders (national, EU and international level) on a voluntary basis (registration to the newsletter is available through the website).

The newsletters are uploaded on the project website and the visitors are able to view and download them. The newsletter issues were also shared on the project's social media profiles, as well as on the JoinUp.

The template of the last Newsletter Issue of the project can be found at the Appendix I of this deliverable.

1.16 Press release

The final SENSE4US press release was created by Gov2u in order to announce the end of project's lifecycle. All press release items during the implementation of the project were uploaded on its website in section "News". The figure below depicts the press release structure with the project logo.

PRESS RELEASE
FOR IMMEDIATE RELEASE

SENSE4US Project completes lifecycle

Brussels, 28/12/2016 - The official ending of the SENSE4US project is due on the 31st of December 2016, thus completing its 39 months lifetime cycle.

SENSE4US rounded off the project's activities with a final conference which took place on the 8th of December 2016 in Brussels, Belgium. The conference event was titled "[Policy Making in a Complex World - Can technology restore trust in European decision-making?](#)" and it brought together parliamentarians, policy makers, academics and civil society members across Europe.

During this one day event participants addressed how new technologies can help support our democracy, revealing a novel path for the future of decision-making. The stakeholders were informed about how digital tools and technologies can enable policy makers' access and summarize a wide array of relevant data, taking into account the views of citizens on policy issues and better acknowledging the implications of proposed policies.

"Politicians nowadays have the ability to reach out to a wide array of people, but in the process of digital communication, discussion fails. Even though there are so many people who follow the latest developments, they choose not to engage in conversation, because they feel disempowered," said Oktavia Hrunn Jónsdóttir, Deputy MP, Icelandic Pirate Party during her webcam participation. She continued by saying *"If politicians wish to win the trust of people, then they mustn't be afraid of saying something "wrong" online, thus motivating the people to further conduct a discussion"*.

This project has been funded with support from the European Commission under the SEVENTH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME

1 | Page

Figure 28 : Press release (page 1)

PRESS RELEASE

FOR IMMEDIATE RELEASE

Furthermore, the latest version of the project's toolkit was showcased to the general public combined with a demo that gave better understanding of each tool's use and possibilities. Specifically, the toolkit brings together the potential to help policy-makers and legislators gain insights through open data, social media sentiment and text analysis and policy simulation.

The project has set the ground for the future of decision making. Soon enough, we hope that the use of the SENSE4US toolkit by policy makers will provide all the necessary resources as well as access to data in order to take into consideration the views of the citizens when forming policies. This will lead in qualitative decision making.

During the project cycle, [University of Southampton – IT Innovation](#) led the consortium that was formed by [The Open University – Knowledge Media Institute](#), [University of Koblenz-Landau – Institute WeST](#), [GESIS-Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences](#), [Government to you \(Gov2u\)](#), [Hansard Society Ltd](#), [eGovlab \(DSV- Stockholm University\)](#).

###

Further information: Sense4Us website: www.sense4us.eu

Contact us: Sense4Us Press Office: communication@sense4us.eu

Social media:

[SENSE4US-project](#)

[SENSE4US-project](#)

[SENSE4US-project](#)

This project has been funded with support from the European Commission under the SEVENTH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME

Figure 29 : Press release (page 2)

2 Project website and social media

2.1 Project website

The Sense4us project website (www.sense4us.eu) is designed, developed and operated by Gov2u. It includes all the relevant information about the project, its goals and objectives, the consortium partners, its WPs, a dedicated news section, a Media section and Links to other projects that Sense4us collaborates with. The website serves as the major dissemination and information channel of the project. It is regularly updated and enriched with new content.

The homepage of the project website is depicted on the following figure.

Figure 30 : Project website

2.2 Project social media profiles

As we have already described in D8.1 (Project dissemination materials), Sense4us has chosen to use the three most popular social media as an additional dissemination channel for the project: Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The links to the project's Social Media profiles are:

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/pages/SENSE4US-project/562585490456097?ref=hl>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/sense4usproject>

LinkedIn: http://www.linkedin.com/profile/view?id=286142319&trk=nav_responsive_tab_profile_pic

Figure 31 : SENSE4US Facebook Page

D8.3 Project Dissemination materials

The screenshot shows the Twitter profile for SENSE4US (@SENSE4USproject). The profile banner features a 'HOLIDAYS' theme with a snowflake and a Santa Claus illustration. The profile statistics are: TWEETS 3,052, FOLLOWING 1,553, FOLLOWERS 629, LIKES 724, LISTS 2, and MOMENTS 0. The bio describes the project as an R&D effort to support policy makers. A pinned tweet from December 9th reads: 'Thanks to everyone who came to #sense4us! If you want to find out more about the project, read our info pack here: [Sense4us Conference Information Pack.pdf]'. Below it is another tweet from December 23rd about the SENSE4US CONFERENCE. The right sidebar shows 'Your Tweet activity' with a bar chart indicating 2,302 impressions over the last week, and a 'Who to follow' list including NESCAFÉ Greece, Aviv Katz, and Linked Research.

Figure 32 : SENSE4US Twitter account

D8.3 Project Dissemination materials

The screenshot displays the LinkedIn profile for the SENSE4US project. The profile header includes the SENSE4US logo, the name 'SENSE4US project', and 'Project' as a category. It shows 467 followers and options to 'Publish a post' and 'View stats'. Below the header, there are tabs for 'Recent Activity (6)', 'Published (53)', 'Drafts (3)', and 'Followers (467)'. The main content area features a grid of posts:

- SENSE4US FINAL CONFERENCE** (December 23, 2016)
- DATA INSIGHTS FOR POLICY MAKERS & CITIZENS** (December 22, 2016)
- SENSE4US-project Flyer is now available!!!** (December 22, 2016)
- Can Technology Improve Our Democracy?** (December 20, 2016)
- The driving force to raise trust in policy making...** (December 8, 2016)
- Policy making in a complex world: can technology...** (December 1, 2016)
- SENSE4US Conference - Policy Making in a Complex...** (November 25, 2016)
- ITProPortal - The rise of Open Data and why it's...** (November 1, 2016)
- publictechnology.net - Lessons from Seoul: How...** (October 17, 2016)
- Joinup - Public review of German municipal...** (October 11, 2016)

Figure 33 : SENSE4US LinkedIn profile

3 Conclusions

D8.3 “Project Dissemination Materials” (M39) presents the updated versions of the dissemination materials of the project, namely the website, newsletter, brochure, poster, flyer, and social media profiles.

Figures incorporated among the chapters of the deliverable, as well as screen shots included in the Appendices are supplementary for the visual representation of the aforementioned materials.

APPENDIX I – Newsletter Issue No.10

The Newsletter Issue No.10 is the last issue of the SENSE4US project. Below the sections of the last issue are depicted.

Editorial

Dear Reader,

The time has come for the SENSE4US project to bid goodbye, at least for now. This project, aiming to enable policy making, kicked off in October of 2013 and completes its cycle in December of 2016 with the current Newsletter Issue.

The articles that follow will take you through the latest SENSE4US news while also update you on relevant publications and events.

Keep in mind that we always like to hear from you, so if you have any comments or suggestions, please feel free to contact us at: communication@sense4us.eu

With this, we'd like to thank you for keeping up with our project's developments and being part of our community during the past 39 months. Hope to see you again soon!!!

Enjoy the reading!

The SENSE4US Dissemination and Communication Team

Project news

→ **Policy Making in a Complex World - Can technology restore trust in European decision-making?**

The SENSE4US consortium organized a successful Final Conference on the 8th of December in Brussels, Belgium.

During this one day event parliamentarians, policy makers, academics and civil society members discussed how digital tools and technologies can enable policy makers access and summarise a wide array of relevant data, taking into account the views of citizens on policy issues and better acknowledging the implications of proposed policies.

Interesting news

→ **ITPRO - Can technology improve our democracy?**

The internet makes it easy to be an armchair activist, retweeting a campaigner's call to action, mass-emailing demands to an MP, or tagging your representative in a Facebook post. (...) The widely held belief that social media and digital tools let us have a real discussion is false. "Technology can help us improve conversation, but if the fundamental interaction at the start of it is misleading or confused, then it doesn't matter how great your hashtag is, how great your Facebook [post] is, or how original your Instagrams, people are going to at some point... feel misled and frustrated, and that there's no point in engaging in the first place."

[Read more](#)

→ **Open eGovernment practices in all EU Member States make public services more collaborative, efficient and inclusive**

In a digital single market, public services should be digital, open and cross-border by design. As part of the eGovernment Action Plan, public administrations and public institutions should be providing borderless user-friendly and end-to-end digital public services to all citizens and businesses by 2020. Two Commission studies highlight how collaborative and digitally-based Open eGovernment Services (OGS) can enhance transparency and responsiveness in citizens' dealings with administration, build trust across sectors and provide better public services.

[Read more](#)

→ **World Resources Institute - The Future of Open Government**

The ultimate potential of open government lies in its ability to improve human wellbeing. Greater public participation in decision making, increased transparency in how public resources are used, and more public scrutiny over decision makers are all vital to deepening democracy in rich and poor countries alike.

Upcoming events

→ March 2017

23 March | 2017 | **Stockholm, Sweden**

Data Innovation Summit - (Data Analytics, Data Science, Data Governance, Customer Analytics, Data Quality, Data Architecture)

→ May 2017

17-19 May | 2017 | **Danube University Krems, Austria**

CeDEM17 – International Conference for E-Democracy and Open Government 2017

Relevant Publications

- [Semantics Analysis of Microblogs](#), Hasan Saif, Knowledge Media Institute, Open University, Milton Keynes, United Kingdom, January 21,2015, pp. 1-225

- [Fossil-free public transport: Prescriptive policy analysis for the Swedish bus fleets](#), Maria Xylia, Osama Ibrahim, Semida Silveira, Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM), IEEE, Porto, Portugal, 2016, pp. 1-5

- [A Linked Open Data Approach for Sentiment Lexicon Adaptation](#), Hassan Saif, Miriam Fernandez, Leon Kastler, and Harith Alani, Proceedings of the Fourth International Workshop on Linked Data for Information Extraction co-located with 15th International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC 2016), October 18, 2016, pp. 11-22

Figure 34 : Project Newsletter